

Role of coordination compounds as good pesticides[†]

R.V. Singh* and Sumit Srivastava

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : rvsjpr@hotmail.com

Manuscript received 25 February 2013, accepted 26 February 2013

Abstract : Pest problem is one of the major constraints for achieving higher production in agriculture crops. India loses about 30% of its crops due to pests and diseases each year. It is estimated that India loses approximately 18% of the crop yield valued at Rs. 90,000-crore due to pest attacks each year only. The use of pesticides in crop protection has certainly contributed for minimizing yield losses. The great increase in the use of pesticides occurred with the development of new organic chemicals. In addition to chemicals for the control of fungi and insects, new developments were nematicides, herbicides, rodenticides, etc. The use of chemicals helped increase productivity, but caused great concern about their effect on human health and safety. Most of the pesticides are obviously organic compounds which behave as good chelating agents towards the metals. It has been seen that the pesticidal activity is enhanced on complexation with the metals. In view of this, many coordination compounds have been designed recently for their specific biocidal action. The biological effect of these derivatives depends on the nature and structure of the ligands and their metal complexes and also on the presence of particular element. Applicability of coordination compounds in the field of bioinorganic chemistry is quite vast. These compounds constitute the minerals, plants and are also present in animals. These play important functions and are of great importance in regulating the various biological functions of plants and animals. Keeping these facts into consideration an attempt has been made to screen some coordination compounds of boron, silicon, tin, manganese and molybdenum for their pesticidal activity. The results showed that with some precautions coordination compounds may act as good pesticides. The findings have been discussed in details.

Keywords : Coordination compounds, pesticides, nematicidal activity, crop plants, antimicrobial activity, spectral studies.

Introduction

The interface between inorganic chemistry and biology has been a rich one dating back several centuries¹. The interaction of transition metal ions with biological molecules provides one of the most fascinating areas of coordination chemistry. In more recent times, this field has been referred to as bioinorganic chemistry. Over the last more than one decade, there has been a dramatic growth of interest in inorganic complexes based materials that exhibit unusual solid properties. Further, recent years have witnessed a great deal of interest in the synthesis and characterization of transition metal complexes containing Schiff bases as ligands due to their applications as catalysts for many reactions² and relation to synthetic and natural oxygen carriers³. The bioactivity of heterocyclic Schiff bases as well as of their metal complexes is of interest, especially due to their pharmaco-

logical properties. Considerable importance has been given to transition metal complexes of azomethine ligands on account of their biological properties⁴. The coordination chelates of sulfur, oxygen, nitrogen and other donor Schiff base systems⁵ have been widely investigated and they frequently show novel structural features⁶, unusual spectral, catalytical⁷ and electrochemical⁸ properties and relevance to biological systems⁹. Plant parasitic nematodes are important agricultural pests. They incur enormous losses to crop productivity as well as marketable quality of the produce. Because of their hidden way of life in soil pore-spaces, their management has become rather tricky. Traditionally they are managed by physical, chemical, biological, cultural and regulatory methods¹⁰.

The applications of metals in environmental systems have led to an upsurge of interest in their effects on growth and development processes in plants. Pesticides, by the

[†]Professor J. C. Ghosh Memorial Lecture (2011) delivered during 49th Annual Convention of Chemists, 2012, organized by the Indian Chemical Society held at National Institute of Technical Teachers' Training and Research, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India on December 12, 2012.

definition are the chemicals which kill pests. The prime requirement for the successful utilization of biologically active compounds in agriculture is that it should be inherently safe both in production and in its application¹¹. This safety should extend not only to man, but also to domestic, farm and wild animals, useful plants, beneficial insects and micro-organisms. The metabolism and mode of action of the compounds are no less important, and toxicological data for metabolites formed in plants, in animals and in the soil, are becoming increasingly essential. Many biologically important Schiff bases have been reported in the literature possessing, antibacterial¹², antifungal¹³, antimicrobial¹⁴, anticonvulsant¹⁵, anti-HIV¹⁶, anti-inflammatory¹⁷ and antitumor¹⁸⁻²⁰ activities. Salicylanilide probably the first compound of carboxylic acid anilides class to be shown to have fungicidal activity. This has been described as a selective protectant which has activity against ascomycetes (e.g. *Aspergillus* sp. and *Cladosporium fulvum*) and phytomycetes (e.g. *Plasmopara viticola*). Several number of substituted carboxylic acid anilides were synthesized and tested for their systemic fungitoxic properties. The substituted carboxylic acid anilides show specific systemic fungicidal activity against basidiomycetes. Transition metal complexes derived from sulfur donor ligands have wide spectrum, ranging from synthesis to application in diverse fields²¹. Sulfonamides were introduced as chemotherapeutic agents in the form of compound, prontosil, which had the effect of curing mice with infections caused by beta-hemolytic streptococci. The sulfonamides have been extremely useful in the treatment of uncomplicated UTI caused by *Escherichia coli*, and in the treatment of meningococcal meningitis because they cross the blood-brain barrier.

In recent years, the coordination behaviour of organometallic compounds of Schiff bases with oxygen, sulfur and nitrogen containing ligands has received great attention as a consequence of their biological property²². The pronounced biological effects of organometallics led to their wide applications in the fields like medicine and agriculture. The ever increasing practical uses of organometallics as biocides in agriculture, as antiknock agents in automobiles and as catalytic agents in a number of industrial (specially biotechnological processes) have led to and increasing concern about their environmental aspects also²³.

Amongst the group 14 organometallics²⁴⁻²⁶, the applications of organosilicon and organotin derivatives have been increasing at a fast rate. In spite of the reservations

arising due to actual as well as potential environmental pollution, a wide variety of organometallic compounds are finding increasing uses as pesticides. For example, hydroxide and acetate of tri-phenyl tin and silicon are both used in numerous formulations for the control of a variety of fungal growths particularly potato blight. Tricyclohexyltin hydroxide is a very effective acaricide for controlling fruit free red spider mite on apples and pears.

The importance of boron as biologically active elements is evinced by the boron compounds containing alkylating groups inhibiting the development of walker 256 carcinosarcoma in rats but less active towards leukemia L₂₁₀ and sarcoma 180 in mice²⁷. Benzoxaborines have been found with the inhibitory properties against various tumors in mice and rats²⁸. The boronhydride complexes of benzothiazepinole derivatives were found to inhibit P³⁸⁸ leukemia cells in mice²⁹. Bicyclic boron compounds have cytotoxic activity³⁰⁻³² and are used for the treatment of certain brain tumors³³.

There has been considerable interest in coordination chemistry of manganese(II) compounds because of their potential utilities as model compounds of manganese containing proteins which would show significant involvement of manganese in various biological systems³⁴. Manganese(II) complexes with Schiff base ligands are becoming increasingly important as biochemical, analytical and antimicrobial reagents, in the design of molecular ferromagnets, in materials chemistry and so on³⁵. Manganese is also important in photosynthetic oxygen evolution in chloroplasts in plants. It is responsible for the terminal photooxidation of water during the light reactions of photosynthesis and has a metalloenzyme core containing four atoms of manganese³⁶. For this reason, most broad-spectrum plant fertilizers contain manganese.

Molybdenum is one of the most biologically active transition element and is an essential micronutrient for micro-organisms, plants and animals³⁷. It possesses a large number of stable accessible oxidation states and higher oxidation states contain mono oxo or *cis*-dioxo molybdenum species. Nature has incorporated molybdenum into a number of redox enzymes³⁸. In dioxo complexes of d^0 transition metals, favourable $p\pi-d\pi$ orbital interactions between the π -base oxo ligands and π -acid metal centres are optimized when a *cis*-geometry is adopted; accordingly, all such complexes exhibit *cis*-geometries³⁹. The

cis-[MoO₂]²⁺ centre dominates the chemistry of *d*⁰ Mo^{VI} complexes and participates in many oxygen atom transfer reactions⁴⁰. Molybdenum complexes find uses as corrosion inhibitors, lubricants and antiwear additives. It is an indispensable constituent of enzymes that are involved in the function of nitrogen fixing nitrogenase.

Molybdenum is recognized in small amounts among all micronutrients. A large number of oxotransfer reactions occurring in the biological world are catalysed by a group of enzymes containing molybdenum in the centre of a dissociable cofactor.

Seeing disadvantage of above mentioned chemical pesticides, we felt the need of new hopeful chemicals and for this purpose we have selected the complexes of five elements, silicon(IV), tin(IV), manganese(II), molybdenum(VI) and boron(III) with biologically active ligands.

These compounds have been tested and have been found to be effective on application and according to the data available these are environmentally safe and not hazardous for human being.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

The R₃SiCl, R₃SnCl, R₂SiCl₂, R₂SnCl₂ and MnCl₂.4H₂O was purchased from Alfa Aesar. Phenylldihydroxyborone [PhB(OH)₂]⁴¹ and dioxobis(2,4-pentanedinato)molybdenum(VI) [MoO₂(C₅H₇O₂)₂] was prepared as described previously⁴². All the reagents were dried and distilled before use. 1-Acetylferrocene, hydrazinehydrochloride, thiosemicarbazide, 3-acetylcoumarin and 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide were purchased from Sisco, Lancaster and Lobachemie and used as such.

Preparation of the ligands :

Preparation of hydrazinecarboxamides (L¹H, L³H and L⁵H₂) :

The hydrazinecarboxamides of 3-acetyl coumarin, 1-acetylferrocene and 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide were prepared by the condensation of 3-acetyl coumarin, 1-acetylferrocene and 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide with hydrazinecarboxamide hydrochloride (in presence of sodium acetate) in 1 : 1 molar ratio using ethanol as a solvent. The contents were refluxed for about 3.5–5 h. After refluxing, the contents were separated out as crys-

talline solids. These were dried and purified by recrystallisation in the same solvent. The analyses and physical properties of these ligands are enlisted in Table 1.

Preparation of hydrazinecarbothioamides (L²H, L⁴H and L⁶H₂) :

The hydrazinecarbothioamides of 3-acetyl coumarin, 1-acetylferrocene and 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide were prepared by the condensation of 3-acetyl coumarin, 1-acetylferrocene and 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide with hydrazinecarbothioamide in 1 : 1 molar ratio in the medium of ethanol. The contents were refluxed for about 4–5 h. After refluxing, the contents were separated out as crystalline solids. These were dried and purified by recrystallisation from the same solvent. The analyses and physical properties of these ligands are enlisted in Table 1.

Preparation of sulfonamide-imine (L⁷H) :

The sulfonamide-imine of 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide was prepared by the condensation of 2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide with sulfathiazole in 1 : 1 molar ratio in the medium of ethanol. The contents were refluxed for about 4–5 h on a water bath. After refluxing, the contents were separated out as crystalline solid. These were dried *in vacuo* and purified by recrystallisation from the same solvent. The analyses and physical properties of these ligands are enlisted in Table 1. The structures of all the seven ligands have been shown in Figs. 1-7.

Preparation of the metal complexes :

Preparation of the boron complexes :

For the preparation of the boron azomethine complexes a calculated amount of PhB(OH)₂ was taken in dry benzene and unimolar and bimolar amount of the monobasic bidentate ligands (L¹H, L²H, L³H, L⁴H and L⁷H) and equimolar amount of bibasic tridentate ligands (L⁵H₂ and L⁶H₂) were added to it. The progress and completion of the reaction was ascertained by observing the liberated water in the form of water-benzene binary azeotrope, which remained immiscible in pure benzene. The excess of the solvent was distilled off and the product was dried *in vacuo*. It was repeatedly washed with dry cyclohexane and again dried under vacuum for two hours.

Table 1. Analytical data and physical properties of the ligands and their metal complexes

Compd.	Colour	Melting point (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)						Molar mass Found (Calcd.)
			C	H	N	S	M		
L ¹ H	Cream	199	53.05 (58.70)	4.65 (4.52)	16.85 (17.13)	-	-	220.69 (245.23)	
L ² H	White	118	55.07 (55.19)	4.35 (4.24)	15.88 (16.08)	12.52 (12.27)	-	239.39 (261.30)	
L ³ H	Yellow	185	52.54 (54.77)	5.89 (5.30)	13.90 (14.74)	-	-	263.52 (285.14)	
L ⁴ H	Yellow	143	50.02 (51.53)	5.08 (5.02)	13.10 (13.99)	10.15 (10.69)	-	327.21 (301.92)	
L ⁵ H ₂	Green	109	61.25 (62.27)	4.81 (5.22)	19.99 (20.74)	-	-	253.49 (270.11)	
L ⁶ H ₂	Green	123	58.94 (59.00)	4.02 (4.92)	18.87 (19.58)	10.91 (11.24)	-	279.24 (286.04)	
L ⁷ H	Green	180	56.12 (58.78)	3.64 (3.81)	11.52 (12.46)	10.32 (10.71)	-	427.56 (449.52)	
[PhB(OH)(L ¹)]	Cream	100	64.65 (62.10)	4.83 (4.63)	13.91 (12.06)	-	3.24 (3.10)	362.46 (348.33)	
[PhB(L ¹) ₂]	Yellow	120	39.86 (62.62)	3.74 (4.34)	8.99 (14.64)	-	1.61 (1.87)	549.73 (575.35)	
[PhB(OH)(L ²)]	Yellow	110	57.69 (59.36)	4.10 (4.42)	11.54 (11.53)	8.92 (8.85)	7.13 (2.96)	348.54 (364.19)	
[PhB(L ²) ₂]	Yellow	130	56.12 (59.35)	4.60 (4.11)	13.25 (13.81)	10.79 (10.57)	1.57 (1.70)	645.31 (607.11)	
[PhB(OH)(L ³)]	Red	158	60.15 (58.89)	4.94 (5.18)	10.02 (10.80)	-	2.14 (2.78)	370.42 (389.06)	
[PhB(L ³) ₂]	Yellow	145	57.10 (58.39)	5.36 (5.05)	12.55 (12.77)	-	1.67 (1.64)	605.01 (658.21)	
[PhB(OH)(L ⁴)]	Brown	140	57.15 (56.23)	4.94 (4.98)	10.00 (10.35)	6.90 (7.11)	2.35 (2.66)	480.12 (405.86)	
[PhB(L ⁴) ₂]	Brown	173	57.15 (58.59)	4.36 (4.81)	12.00 (12.15)	8.90 (9.27)	1.70 (1.56)	646.56 (691.63)	
[PhB(L ⁵)]	Red	145	67.60 (64.06)	5.10 (5.66)	14.44 (15.73)	-	3.13 (3.03)	338.50 (356.11)	
[PhB(L ⁶)]	Pink	164	61.00 (61.33)	3.04 (3.41)	14.90 (15.01)	7.97 (8.61)	2.40 (2.90)	360.42 (372.06)	
[PhB(L ⁷) ₂]	Brown	130	61.15 (62.89)	2.94 (3.71)	10.82 (10.44)	11.00 (11.51)	2.14 (2.01)	567.42 (535.42)	
[Ph ₂ Si(Cl)(L ¹)]	Yellow	140	67.05 (62.20)	4.65 (4.30)	9.85 (9.04)	-	5.98 (6.08)	400.69 (463.15)	
[Ph ₂ Si(L ¹) ₂]	White	122	65.07 (64.29)	4.35 (4.50)	11.88 (12.44)	-	4.52 (4.30)	649.39 (672.62)	
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(Cl)(L ¹)]	Light yellow	148	50.54 (50.37)	4.89 (4.81)	13.41 (12.54)	-	7.78 (8.47)	393.52 (333.82)	
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ¹) ₂]	Yellow	218	58.02 (57.53)	5.08 (4.82)	7.10 (7.73)	-	5.95 (5.19)	557.21 (543.20)	
[Ph ₂ Si(Cl)(L ²)]	White	160	60.25 (60.10)	4.51 (4.22)	8.99 (8.74)	6.46 (6.70)	5.76 (5.89)	443.49 (479.23)	
[Ph ₂ Si(L ²) ₂]	White	175	61.94 (61.44)	4.12 (4.30)	10.87 (11.98)	9.21 (9.14)	3.47 (3.99)	699.24 (704.05)	
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(Cl)(L ²)]	Yellow	180	46.12 (48.00)	4.64 (4.60)	12.52 (12.03)	9.32 (9.11)	8.96 (8.09)	357.56 (349.89)	
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ²) ₂]	White	190	56.65 (54.43)	4.83 (4.53)	13.91 (14.62)	11.21 (11.15)	4.24 (4.88)	702.46 (574.68)	
[Ph ₂ Si(Cl)(L ³)]	Yellow	120	58.86 (59.82)	3.74 (4.84)	8.99 (8.34)	-	5.31 (5.61)	549.73 (504.88)	
[Ph ₂ Si(L ³) ₂]	Yellow	130	61.69 (60.11)	5.54 (5.10)	11.54 (11.20)	-	4.13 (3.76)	698.54 (755.71)	
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(Cl)(L ³)]	Light yellow	210	46.12 (47.75)	2.90 (5.31)	10.25 (11.11)	-	7.57 (7.44)	345.31 (375.71)	
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ³) ₂]	Light yellow	245	60.15 (53.69)	5.94 (5.47)	12.82 (13.44)	-	4.14 (4.50)	667.42 (624.45)	
[Ph ₂ Si(Cl)(L ⁴)]	Light yellow	133	57.80 (57.89)	4.74 (4.66)	8.93 (8.10)	5.99 (6.18)	5.56 (5.42)	545.73 (520.66)	
[Ph ₂ Si(L ⁴) ₂]	Yellow	158	57.69 (58.21)	4.54 (4.88)	10.54 (10.10)	8.13 (8.16)	3.13 (3.58)	778.04 (789.81)	
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(Cl)(L ⁴)]	Yellow	147	47.12 (45.65)	5.90 (5.11)	10.20 (10.65)	8.07 (8.14)	7.00 (7.14)	375.30 (391.51)	
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ⁴) ₂]	Yellow	178	50.85 (50.99)	5.64 (5.19)	12.62 (12.74)	9.14 (9.70)	4.87 (4.26)	687.12 (656.85)	

Table-1 (contd.)

[Ph ₂ Sn(CI)(L ¹)]	160	Yellow	160	52.05 (52.00)	3.35 (3.60)	7.85 (7.58)	-	21.98 (21.48)	520.19 (553.75)
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ¹) ₂]	162-165	Whitish yellow	162-165	55.00 (56.69)	3.35 (3.96)	11.28 (11.04)	-	31.52 (15.55)	790.69 (763.00)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(CI)(L ¹)]	158	Dark yellow	158	39.54 (39.92)	4.80 (4.74)	9.34 (9.94)	-	26.76 (27.97)	493.52 (424.42)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ¹) ₂]	188	Yellow	188	48.00 (49.26)	4.58 (4.13)	13.10 (13.29)	-	18.00 (18.72)	650.81 (633.88)
[Ph ₂ Sn(CI)(L ²)]	160	White	160	58.90 (50.58)	3.22 (3.52)	7.07 (7.38)	5.80 (5.64)	18.00 (20.84)	563.49 (569.88)
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ²) ₂]	175	White	175	56.72 (54.41)	3.40 (3.80)	10.02 (10.58)	20.32 (20.71)	14.26 (14.99)	789.24 (794.65)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(CI)(L ²)]	175-177	Yellow	175-177	36.15 (38.16)	3.10 (3.65)	7.01 (9.54)	7.04 (7.28)	24.21 (26.97)	415.56 (440.65)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ²) ₂]	182-184	Whitish yellow	182-184	43.10 (46.96)	3.20 (3.95)	12.34 (12.64)	7.04 (7.28)	16.54 (17.84)	602.36 (625.28)
[Ph ₂ Sn(CI)(L ³)]	180-182	Yellow	180-182	59.26 (50.55)	4.53 (4.24)	7.49 (7.07)	-	18.60 (19.58)	559.70 (594.89)
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ³) ₂]	192-194	Yellow	192-194	56.60 (53.91)	4.13 (4.76)	9.24 (9.93)	-	13.53 (14.06)	828.53 (846.36)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(CI)(L ³)]	168-171	Light yellow	168-171	36.72 (38.75)	4.20 (4.55)	9.20 (9.01)	-	23.37 (25.52)	432.61 (465.65)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ³) ₂]	168-170	Light yellow	168-170	46.10 (47.03)	5.90 (5.07)	10.80 (11.74)	-	16.84 (16.60)	767.42 (715.05)
[Ph ₂ Sn(CI)(L ⁴)]	178-179	Dark yellow	178-179	47.00 (49.20)	4.35 (4.12)	6.35 (6.88)	5.08 (5.26)	18.58 (19.48)	620.59 (610.95)
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ⁴) ₂]	160-163	Light brown	160-163	50.07 (51.99)	4.68 (4.59)	9.28 (9.57)	7.42 (7.35)	12.92 (13.51)	740.60 (878.49)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(CI)(L ⁴)]	196	Yellow	196	39.50 (37.45)	4.28 (4.3)	8.14 (8.74)	6.19 (6.67)	25.46 (24.67)	463.82 (481.72)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ⁴) ₂]	184	Yellow	184	46.08 (45.02)	4.18 (4.85)	12.00 (11.24)	8.16 (8.58)	16.44 (15.88)	756.51 (747.18)
[Ph ₂ Si(L ⁵)]	150	Light yellow	150	67.04 (69.19)	4.45 (4.90)	12.35 (12.44)	-	6.98 (6.26)	430.63 (451.75)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ⁵)]	192	White	192	59.04 (59.62)	5.19 (5.61)	16.01 (17.39)	-	8.70 (3.67)	343.62 (322.32)
[Ph ₂ Si(L ⁶)]	169	White	169	65.47 (66.80)	4.75 (4.80)	11.80 (11.99)	6.30 (6.86)	5.50 (5.99)	479.30 (467.02)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ⁶)]	178	White	178	68.02 (56.83)	5.00 (5.32)	16.70 (16.59)	9.37 (9.50)	8.85 (8.28)	357.21 (338.40)
[Ph ₂ Si(L ⁷) ₂]	160-163	White	160-163	65.20 (64.77)	3.70 (3.98)	8.90 (8.88)	10.96 (10.17)	4.16 (4.49)	643.39 (630.63)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ⁷) ₂]	175-178	White	175-178	58.90 (57.44)	4.00 (4.19)	11.87 (11.17)	12.51 (12.74)	6.40 (6.62)	519.20 (501.65)
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ⁵)]	177	Light yellow	177	56.74 (57.55)	4.10 (4.05)	10.54 (10.33)	-	22.30 (21.88)	522.41 (542.35)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ⁵)]	158	Light yellow	158	46.22 (46.53)	4.60 (4.37)	12.30 (13.54)	-	26.64 (28.70)	460.52 (412.98)
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ⁶)]	165	Dark yellow	165	57.20 (55.92)	3.35 (3.97)	9.95 (10.08)	5.23 (5.77)	21.50 (21.28)	540.50 (558.40)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ⁶)]	178	Light yellow	178	45.05 (44.79)	4.61 (4.22)	12.98 (13.05)	7.02 (7.45)	27.44 (27.66)	440.00 (429.04)
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ⁷) ₂]	145	Yellow	145	59.45 (56.55)	3.20 (3.46)	7.07 (7.44)	8.32 (8.87)	15.34 (16.44)	763.80 (721.58)
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ⁷) ₂]	189	Yellow	189	47.70 (48.66)	3.10 (3.55)	9.16 (9.44)	9.10 (10.82)	19.53 (20.04)	546.50 (592.22)
[MnCl(L ¹)H ₂ O]	202	Light brown	202	38.55 (40.87)	3.58 (3.42)	12.16 (11.91)	-	15.43 (15.57)	340.51 (352.62)
[Mn(L ¹) ₂]	210	Light yellow	210	52.83 (53.05)	38.27 (37.08)	16.17 (15.43)	-	9.99 (10.10)	530.51 (543.36)
[MnCl(L ²)H ₂ O]	244	Light yellow	244	40.29 (39.09)	3.12 (3.28)	10.95 (11.39)	8.43 (8.69)	14.28 (14.89)	376.24 (368.68)
[Mn(L ²) ₂]	256	Reddish brown	256	49.20 (50.09)	3.66 (3.50)	16.47 (14.60)	8.22 (8.03)	10.00 (9.54)	562.81 (575.45)
[MnCl(L ³)H ₂ O]	264	Reddish brown	264	37.00 (39.80)	4.81 (4.12)	10.99 (10.74)	-	13.55 (13.99)	343.49 (392.48)
[Mn(L ³) ₂]	268	Light yellow	268	51.90 (50.11)	4.82 (4.92)	13.87 (13.48)	-	8.47 (8.81)	679.24 (623.25)
[MnCl(L ⁴)H ₂ O]	205	Light pink	205	36.56 (38.20)	3.63 (3.99)	10.52 (10.28)	7.32 (7.81)	11.96 (13.44)	457.56 (408.59)

Table-1 (contd.)

[Mn(L ⁴) ₂]	Light pink	209	46.46 (47.63)	4.80 (4.33)	12.90 (12.82)	9.21 (9.75)	7.24 (8.35)	702.46 (655.28)
[Mn(L ⁵)H ₂ O]	Red	236	47.00 (49.30)	4.47 (4.10)	16.65 (16.44)	21.98 (22.08)	-	330.69 (341.40)
[Mn(L ⁶)H ₂ O]	Pink	248	45.07 (47.09)	3.39 (3.99)	15.64 (15.64)	8.52 (8.98)	15.98 (15.28)	349.30 (357.30)
[Mn(L ⁷) ₂]	Reddish brown	234	47.12 (50.77)	3.69 (3.31)	10.20 (10.76)	12.79 (12.32)	11.57 (10.55)	545.01 (520.41)
[MoO ₂ (L ¹) ₂]	Black	198	41.15 (46.89)	3.94 (3.27)	13.80 (13.64)	-	14.56 (15.57)	647.42 (615.93)
[MoO ₂ (L ²) ₂]	Dark green	248	47.05 (44.48)	3.61 (3.10)	12.99 (12.94)	9.56 (9.87)	13.76 (14.79)	623.49 (648.08)
[MoO ₂ (L ³) ₂]	Yellowish green	196	46.76 (44.71)	4.55 (4.02)	12.87 (12.08)	-	13.47 (13.72)	679.24 (698.21)
[MoO ₂ (L ⁴) ₂]	Mustard yellow	184	41.10 (42.75)	3.68 (3.89)	11.52 (11.50)	8.32 (8.78)	12.96 (13.13)	757.50 (730.34)
[MoO ₂ (L ⁵) ₂]	Mustard yellow	185	43.65 (42.43)	3.38 (3.53)	14.91 (14.12)	-	23.24 (24.25)	372.46 (396.20)
[MoO ₂ (L ⁶) ₂]	Black	208	39.05 (40.77)	4.83 (3.39)	13.85 (13.58)	7.32 (7.78)	22.32 (23.28)	430.63 (412.47)
[MoO ₂ (L ⁷) ₂]	Black	196	44.56 (45.92)	2.35 (2.97)	8.88 (9.74)	11.52 (11.14)	15.98 (16.73)	564.14 (575.40)

Fig. 1. 3-Acetyl coumarin hydrazinecarboxamide (L¹H).

Fig. 2. 3-Acetyl coumarin hydrazinecarbothioamide (L²H).

Fig. 3. 1-Acetylferrocene hydrazinecarboxamide (L³H).

Fig. 4. 1-Acetylferrocene hydrazinecarbothioamide (L⁴H).

Fig. 5. 2-Hydroxy-N-phenylbenzamide hydrazinecarboxamide (L⁵H₂).

Fig. 6. 2-Hydroxy-N-phenylbenzamide hydrazinecarbothioamide (L⁶H₂).

Fig. 7. 2-Hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide sulfathiazole (L^7H).

Preparation of the organosilicon and organotin complexes :

For the preparation of these complexes, a weighed amount of R_3SiCl , R_3SnCl , R_2SiCl_2 and R_2SnCl_2 in dry methanol was added in the methanolic solution of the sodium salts of the monobasic bidentate ligands in 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 stoichiometric ratios and only in 1 : 1 molar ratio in case of bifunctional tridentate ligands. The resulting mixture was heated under reflux for 14–18 h, the precipitate of sodium chloride formed during the course of the reaction was removed by filtration and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The product was dried *in vacuo*. The resulting compounds were washed and recrystallized with methanol and *n*-hexane.

Preparation of the manganese and molybdenum complexes :

The exact amount of $MnCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ and $[MoO_2(C_5H_7O_2)_2]$ with ligands in methanol were refluxed for 10–12 h. The product was dried *in vacuo*. The resulting compounds were washed and recrystallized with methanol and *n*-hexane.

Physical measurements and analytical methods :

All the sets of ligands and their complexes prepared were subjected to various physicochemical measurements. The molecular weights were determined by the Rast Camphor method⁴³ and conductivity measurements were made with a Systronic Model 305 conductivity bridge. Sulfur was estimated as $BaSO_4$ by the Messenger's⁴⁴ method and nitrogen was determined by the Kjeldahl's method⁴⁵. Carbon and hydrogen analyses were performed at the Central Drug Research Institute (CDRI), Lucknow.

Boron was estimated as boronic acid in presence of mannitol using phenolphthalein as an indicator. Manganese was estimated complexometrically with EDTA using Erichrome Black T as an indicator⁴⁶. Molybdenum was determined gravimetrically as bis(8-hydroxyquino-

lato)dioxomolybdenum(VI) $[MoO_2(C_9H_6OH)_2]$ by the standard method⁴⁷. Tin and silicon were determined gravimetrically as SnO_2 ⁴⁸ and SiO_2 ⁴⁹. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Nicolet Megna FTIR-550 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. Electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in methanol on a UV-160A, Shimadzu spectrophotometer in the range 200–600 nm. 1H , ^{11}B , ^{13}C , ^{29}Si and ^{119}Sn NMR spectra were recorded using a JEOL-AL-300 FT NMR spectrometer in DMSO- d_6 . EPR spectra of the complexes were monitored on Varian E-4X band spectrometer at SAIF, IIT Madras, Chennai and X-ray diffraction spectra of the compounds were obtained on the Philips P.W. 1840 automatic diffractometer. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC.

Pharmacology :

Antimicrobial screening :

Antifungal studies :

Bioefficacies of the ligands and their metal complexes were checked *in vitro* as well as *in vivo*. The *in vitro* antifungal activities of the ligands and their complexes have been evaluated against pathogenic fungi, *Alternaria alternata*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum* by the agar plate technique⁵⁰. The potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium was prepared in the laboratory to maintain the fungal growth. For PDA preparation, 20 g potato was extracted with distilled water (100 mL) at 100 °C for 1 h and it was filtered off by cotton filter. The potato juice was then mixed with 2 g dextrose and 1.5 g agar and finally the pH of the prepared PDA media was adjusted at 7. Solutions of the test compounds in methanol at 100 and 200 ppm concentrations were prepared and then were mixed with the medium. The medium then was poured into petri plates and the spores of fungi were placed on the medium with the help of inoculum's needle. These petriplates were wrapped in the polythene bags containing a few drops of alcohol and were placed in an incubator at 25 ± 2 °C. The activity was determined after 96 h of incubation at room temperature (25 °C). The controls were also run and three replicates were used in each case. The linear growth of the fungus was obtained by measuring the diameter of the fungal colony after four days and the percentage inhibition was calculated as $100 \times (C - T)/C$, where C = diameter of the fungus colony in the control plate after 96 h and T = diameter of the fungal colony in the test plates after the same period. The antifungal screen-

ing data of compounds were compared with the standard (Flucanazole).

Antibacterial screening :

In vitro antibacterial screening is generally performed by disc diffusion method⁵¹ for primary selection of the compounds as bioactive agents. The antibacterial activity of the ligands and their complexes were evaluated against the bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The nutrient agar medium having the composition peptone 5 g, beef extract 5 g, NaCl 5 g, agar-agar 20 g and distilled water 1000 mL was pipetted into the petridish. When it solidified, 5 mL of warm seeded agar was applied. The seeded agar was prepared by cooling the molten agar to 40 °C and then added the 10 mL of bacterial suspension. The compounds were dissolved in methanol in 500 and 1000 ppm concentrations. Paper discs of Whatman No. 1 filter paper measuring diameter of 5 mm were soaked in these solutions of varied concentrations. The discs were dried and placed on the medium previously seeded with organisms in petriplates at suitable distance. The petriplates were stored in an incubator at 28 ± 2 °C for 24 h. The diameters of the zone of inhibition produced by the compounds were compared with the standard antibiotic (Streptomycin). The zone of inhibition thus formed around each disc containing the test compounds was measured accurately in mm.

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) :

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration, MIC, is the lowest concentration of test agent that inhibited visible growth of bacteria after 18 h incubation at 37 °C. The determination of the MIC involves a semi quantitative test procedure, which gives an approximation to the least concentration of an antimicrobial needed to prevent microbial growth. The minimum inhibitory concentration was determined by liquid dilution method⁵². Stock solutions of metal complexes with 14–35 mg/mL concentrations were prepared with aqueous methanol solvent. Inoculum of the overnight culture was prepared. In a series of tubes, 1 mL each of metal complexes solutions with different concentrations were taken and 0.4 mL of the inoculum was added to each tubes. Further 3.5 mL of the sterile water was added to each of the test tubes. These test tubes were incubated for 24 h and observed for the presence of tur-

bidity. The absorbance of the suspension of the inoculum was observed with spectrophotometer at 555 nm. The end result of the test was the minimum concentration of antimicrobial (test materials) which gave a clear solution, i.e. no visual growth⁵³.

Pesticidal activity :

Pesticidal activity of the synthesized compounds was checked *in vitro* as well as *in vivo*. The *in vitro* pesticidal activity of ligands and their complexes have been evaluated against three adult beetles *Chorotogonus trachyp-terus*, *Helicoverpa armigera* and *Spodoptera litura* which were used for the experiment. Rearing of insects was maintained at the storage section of Division of Entomology, Agricultural Research Institute, Durgapura, Jaipur, in a laboratory for bioassay. All compounds were weighed and dissolved in methanol to prepare 500, 200, and 100 ppm solutions. One mL of each concentration of various compounds was directly poured in each petri plate (90 mm) with the help of a micropipette. Petri plates with test solution were rotated vigorously to prepare uniform film and allowed to dry for 3–5 min. A thin layer was prepared in the petri dishes (10 cm in diameter) using solution after drying at room temperature. Thirty insects were released in treated petri dishes. These were kept in an incubator at a fixed temperature (30 ± 0.5 °C) along with a control and experiment was replicated thrice. The mortality of these beetles was observed after 96 h. A simple microscope was used to check natural movement of the pests. The mortality percentage was calculated by using Abbott's formula⁵⁴ :

$$P_t = \frac{P_o - P_c}{100 - P_c} \times 100$$

where P_t = corrected mortality (%), P_o = observed mortality (%), and P_c = controlled mortality (%).

In vivo pesticidal activity is generally performed by percent disease incidence (PDI) technique⁵⁵ for primary selection of the compounds as pesticidal agents. Some ligands and their complexes have been screened *in vivo* to check their potency on some crop plants using percent disease incidence (PDI) technique.

- Brinjal-leaf spot disease caused by *Alternaria alternata*.

- Bajra-rust disease caused by *Puccinia penniciti*.
- Bajra-disease, ergot on earhead caused by *Cleviceps fusiformis*.
- Guar-disease, guar blight by *Alternaria symopsidae*.

The percent disease incidence (PDI) technique is the area covered on foliage by specific disease. The percent disease incidence (PDI) was assessed by recording the number of plants showing disease symptoms and the total number of plants examined. Ten plants were examined randomly and scored for percent disease incidence (PDI) by using following formula :

$$PDI = \frac{\text{Some of numerical values of leaves/plants}}{\text{No. of leaves/plants observed} \times \text{maximum rating [10]}} \times 100$$

Nematicidal activity :

Nematicidal activity was carried out on *Meloidogyne incognita*. Nematode *M. incognita* is known to attack more than 3000 host plants⁵⁶. The yields of okra, tomato, and brinjal typically suffer 90.9%, 46.2%, and 2.3% losses, respectively, due to *M. incognita*. *Meloidogyne incognita* produces galls on the roots of many host plants and is responsible for 44.87% yield loss in brinjal. The root-knot nematode produces galls on the roots of many vegetables, pulses, some fruit crops, tobacco, and ornamental crops and causes severe losses.

(a) Ovicidal action :

Clean *M. incognita* eggs were obtained by the reported method. Egg masses were separated from heavily infected brinjal roots and washed under running water. After cutting the roots, 1% of sodium hypochlorite solution was added, shaken, and then sieved through 150 and 400 sieves. Then the eggs of nematode were counted. A total of 150 eggs of nematode *M. incognita* were used per replicate sample and each treatment was replicated three times. The experiment was conducted at $(30 \pm 0.2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$. The eggs were treated with compounds dissolved in 100 and 200 ppm for 24 h and observations in relation to hatching of eggs were noted. The nematicidal activity was calculated using the following formula :

$$N_A (\%) = \frac{H_T}{H_C} \times 100$$

where N_A is the nematicidal activity, H_C is the amount of hatching in the control and H_T is the amount of hatching in the test plate.

(c) Larvicidal action :

Larvicidal efficiency of chemicals was assessed by feeding method. First instar larvae separated from the subculture, were kept in a vials containing 5 g of topically treated wheat grains with 1 mL 100 and 200 ppm concentration of chemicals. Larvae were allowed to continue their development on this diet until the pupae formation. Three replicates were set for each dose along with the control and after 48 h, total emergence and pupal mortality was recorded. Percent larval mortality and corrected larval mortality were calculated by using Abbott's formula.

(b) Pupicidal action :

Last larval instars were stored out from the subculture and were kept in separate container on the same rearing media; pupae of known age (0–12 h) were taken out and were dipped in 100 and 200 ppm concentration of chemical. Three replicates were set for each dose along with the control and after 72 h, total emergence and pupal mortality was recorded. Percent pupal mortality and corrected pupal mortality were calculated by using Abbott's formula.

(d) Adulticidal action :

Adult were stored out from the subculture and were kept in separate container on the same rearing media; adult were dipped in 100 and 200 ppm concentration of chemical. Three replicates were set for each dose along with the control and after 96 h. Percent adult mortality and corrected adult mortality were calculated by using Abbott's formula.

Plant growth regulating activity :

Some ligands and their metal complexes were tested for their plant growth regulating activity against gram plant. Two types of experiments were conducted. In the first experiment, seeds were treated with an aqueous solution of the synthesized complexes by the following germination test method. The germination was followed by the Towel Paper method. Two brown coloured towel papers of equal size (46 cm × 27 cm) for each test were jointly soaked in different concentrations (5, 10, and 25

ppm) of the ligand and its complexes for treated experiments and in water for controlled experiment for 4 h and placed over a butter paper (39 cm × 25 cm). One hundred seeds were placed at an equal distance over the towel papers, which were subsequently covered by another moist towel paper (46 cm × 27 cm). Then the towel paper was rolled up, two ends of the towel paper tied lightly with a rubber band and placed in a germination chamber at 25 ± 1 °C. One hundred seeds were used for each sample. The observations for percent germination and normal seedling were recorded on the 4th and 8th days. The seedlings, which possessed the ability to develop into fully normal and healthy plants, were considered as normal seedlings. In the second experiment, the seeds were treated with physiologically active concentration of the plant growth regulators solution for 6 h at room temperature and drying them to the original moisture level by a hot air circulating oven. After that, uniform size seeds were placed on Whatman No. 1 filter paper lying in the glass petri plates. Each petri plate has 15 seeds placed at equidistance. The filter papers were moistened with fresh solutions of required concentrations.

Results and discussion

The reactions of [PhB(OH)₂] with the monobasic bidentate ligands N[∧]OH and N[∧]SH in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios and with bibasic tridentate ligands HO[∧]N[∧]OH and HO[∧]N[∧]SH in 1 : 1 molar ratio have been carried out in dry benzene medium. The reactions proceed with the liberation of water, which is removed azeotropically in the form of binary azeotrope of benzene and water as depicted by the following equations :

where, N[∧]X and O[∧]N[∧]X = donor system of organic moiety; X = O or S.

All the newly synthesized compounds are monomeric in nature as indicated by their molecular weight determinations and soluble in DMF, DMSO and MeOH.

For the preparation of diorganometal complexes of silicon and tin with azomethines the reactions of R₂SiCl₂ and R₂SnCl₂ with the sodium salts of monobasic bidentate ligands N[∧]OH and N[∧]SH in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios have been carried out in dry methanol and with bibasic tridentate ligands HO[∧]N[∧]OH and HO[∧]N[∧]SH, the reactions have been carried out in 1 : 1 molar ratio in presence of dry methanol. These reactions proceed with the precipitation of sodium chloride which is removed by filtration and can be represented by the following general equations :

where, R = Me or Ph and M = Si and Sn; N[∧]X and O[∧]N[∧]X = donor system of organic moiety; X = O and S.

The 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar reactions of MnCl₂.4H₂O with the monobasic bidentate ligands N[∧]OH and N[∧]SH have been carried out in methanol. The successive replacement of chloride resulted in the formation of products [MnCl(N[∧]X)H₂O] and [Mn(N[∧]X)₂]. The reactions of MnCl₂.4H₂O with the bibasic tridentate ligands HO[∧]N[∧]OH and HO[∧]N[∧]SH have been carried out in 1 : 1 molar ratio in methanolic medium. The reactions proceed with the liberation of HCl and water. These reactions can be represented by the following general equations :

The reactions of dioxobis(2,4-pentanedionato)molybdenum(VI) with the monobasic bidentate ligands were carried out in 1 : 2 molar ratios and with the bibasic tridentate ligands in 1 : 1 molar ratio in dry methanol. The reactions proceed with the liberation of two molecules of 2,4-pentanedione. The resulting coloured solids are diamagnetic.

The bonding pattern and the geometry of these com-

plexes have been deduced on the basis of UV, IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, ESR spectral and X-ray powder diffraction studies. The physical properties and analytical data of the ligands and their metal complexes are enlisted in Table 1.

IR spectra :

The significant IR bands of the ligands and their metal complexes along with their tentative assignments are reported in Table 2 used for the establishment of the mode of the coordination of ligands towards the metal ion. The IR spectra of all the ligands display a sharp band at 1605–1622 cm⁻¹ due to the (>C=N) group which is shifted towards lower as well as higher region (10–15 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of the corresponding metal complexes, probably due to change in electron density of the azomethine linkage (>C=N)^{57,58}, leads to coordination of ligands through the azomethine nitrogen to the metal atom. In the IR spectra of the ligands, two common sharp bands observed around 3340 and 3400 cm⁻¹ are due to ν_{sym} and ν_{asym} vibrations of NH₂ group, respectively. The position of these bands does not alter in the metal complexes and thus indicates the non-involvement of nitrogen atom of NH₂ group in coordination. A medium intensity band appears in the region 3210–3240 cm⁻¹ due to ν(NH) mode in the ligands is absent in the spectra of

Table 2. IR spectral data of the ligands and their metal complexes

Compd.	IR spectral data (cm ⁻¹)					
	ν(C=N)	ν(NH)	ν(M←N)	ν(M←S)	ν(M-O)	ν(M-Cl)
L ¹ H	1620	3222	-	-	-	-
L ² H	1610	3230	-	-	-	-
L ³ H	1607	3240	-	-	-	-
L ⁴ H	1605	3210	-	-	-	-
L ⁵ H ₂	1616	3234	-	-	-	-
L ⁶ H ₂	1622	-	-	-	-	-
L ⁷ H	1613	-	-	-	-	-
[PhB(OH)(L ¹)]	1605	-	1523	-	1360	-
[PhB(L ¹) ₂]	1603	-	1520	-	1355	-
[PhB(OH)(L ²)]	1596	-	1514	838	1356	-
[PhB(L ²) ₂]	1599	-	1511	836	1325	-
[PhB(OH)(L ³)]	1590	-	1500	-	1322	-
[PhB(L ³) ₂]	1597	-	1525	-	1330	-
[PhB(OH)(L ⁴)]	1589	-	1488	834	1352	-
[PhB(L ⁴) ₂]	1595	-	1520	840	1340	-
[PhB(L ⁵)]	1598	-	1498	-	1335	-

Table-2 (contd.)

[PhB(L ⁶)]	1609	-	1520	839	1328	-
[PhB(L ⁷) ₂]	1593	-	1485	837	1320	-
[Ph ₂ Si(Cl)(L ¹)]	1610	-	520	-	594	415
[Ph ₂ Si(L ¹) ₂]	1607	-	488	-	596	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(Cl)(L ²)]	1600	-	502	530	560	417
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ²) ₂]	1605	-	486	523	620	-
[Ph ₂ Si(Cl)(L ³)]	1586	-	479	-	594	419
[Ph ₂ Si(L ³) ₂]	1585	-	489	-	596	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(Cl)(L ⁴)]	1596	-	505	525	634	415
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ⁴) ₂]	1590	-	513	526	630	-
[Ph ₂ Si(L ⁵)]	1603	-	518	-	590	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ⁶)]	1609	-	505	524	540	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ⁷) ₂]	1606	-	486	530	620	-
[Ph ₂ Sn(Cl)(L ¹)]	1599	-	414	-	530	320
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ¹) ₂]	1593	-	425	-	525	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(Cl)(L ²)]	1590	-	415	348	535	316
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ²) ₂]	1587	-	410	360	530	-
[Ph ₂ Sn(Cl)(L ³)]	1599	-	416	-	525	317
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ³) ₂]	1604	-	418	-	523	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(Cl)(L ⁴)]	1607	-	420	350	522	315
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ⁴) ₂]	1613	-	425	348	527	-
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ⁵)]	1610	-	420	-	528	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ⁶)]	1614	-	422	346	526	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ⁷) ₂]	1606	-	420	355	525	-
[MnCl(L ¹)H ₂ O]	1610	-	490	-	644	318
[Mn(L ¹) ₂]	1612	-	500	-	585	-
[MnCl(L ²)H ₂ O]	1605	-	500	333	600	321
[Mn(L ²) ₂]	1600	-	495	347	636	-
[MnCl(L ³)H ₂ O]	1601	-	475	-	640	322
[Mn(L ³) ₂]	1605	-	488	-	597	-
[MnCl(L ⁴)H ₂ O]	1593	-	490	320	598	317
[Mn(L ⁴) ₂]	1598	-	510	320	640	-
[Mn(L ⁵)H ₂ O]	1604	-	499	-	634	-
[Mn(L ⁶)H ₂ O]	1609	-	513	350	597	-
[Mn(L ⁷) ₂]	1598	-	500	326	610	-
[MoO ₂ (L ¹) ₂]	1612	-	480	-	660	-
[MoO ₂ (L ²) ₂]	1597	-	508	420	650	-
[MoO ₂ (L ³) ₂]	1589	-	488	-	645	-
[MoO ₂ (L ⁴) ₂]	1594	-	455	433	652	-
[MoO ₂ (L ⁵)]	1607	-	490	-	655	-
[MoO ₂ (L ⁶)]	1611	-	504	428	650	-
[MoO ₂ (L ⁷) ₂]	1607	-	511	425	655	-

the metal complexes, which indicates the expected deprotonation of functional group on complexation. The bands at 1690–1700 cm⁻¹ due to ν(C=O) vibrations ap-

pear in the spectra of free ligands are shifted towards lower frequency in the spectra of the metal complexes due to the keto-enol tautomerization and coordination of

oxygen to the central metal atom⁵⁹. The band due to $\nu(>C=S)$ modes in the spectra of the ligands is observed at 1000–1040 cm^{-1} . This band shifted to lower frequency⁶⁰ in the spectra of the metal complexes suggesting tautomerization of the ligands and their chelation through the thiolic sulfur. This fact is further corroborated by the observation of the new bands due to $\nu(C-O)/\nu(C-S)$ mode at lower frequency in the spectra of metal complexes. In the spectra of free ligands the band at 1720 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu(C=O)$ of the lactone moiety⁶¹ which remains unchanged in the spectra of metal complexes indicating that the lactone oxygen is not involved in coordination.

The mode of coordination is further supported by the appearance of new bands in the spectra of metal complexes at – 1525–1488 cm^{-1} ($\nu B-N$), 1360–1320 cm^{-1} ($\nu B-O$), $838 \pm 2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu B-S$), $480 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu Si-N$), $417 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu Si-Cl$), $620 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu Si-O$), $525 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu Si-S$), $420 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu Sn-N$), $530 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu Sn-O$), $360 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu Sn-S$), $480 \pm 25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu Mn-N$), $250 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu Mn-Cl$), $650 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu Mo-O$), $425 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu Mo-S$) and $355 \pm 4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu Mo-N$).

In the spectra of 1 : 1 manganese metal complexes a band is observed in the range 860–870 cm^{-1} which may be attributed to the coordinated water molecule. Further, a broad band around 3500–3550 cm^{-1} may be due to $\nu(O-H)$ of water molecule. This band is absent in the

case of 1 : 2 complexes. In case of dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes, new bands observed in the regions 920–910 cm^{-1} and 900–980 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu_{\text{sym}}(O=Mo=O)$ and $\nu_{\text{asym}}(O=Mo=O)$ indicating a *cis*- MoO_2 structure.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the ligands and their metal derivatives have been recorded in methanol. The electronic spectra of the organic moieties exhibit two intense maxima at *ca.* 260–297 and 370–385 nm. The band in the region 260–297 nm is assignable to $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions of the benzenoid group of ligands, which undergoes red shift in the spectra of metal complexes due to the large conjugation system resulting in lowering of energy between π and π^* orbitals. The second band at 370–385 nm ($n-\pi^*$) of azomethine group undergoes a blue shift on complexation due to the coordination of nitrogen atom to the central metal atom. This shift occurs due to the donation of a lone pair of electrons by the nitrogen of the ligand to the central atom. All the complexes show an absorption maximum in the region 430–510 nm in the visible region, which probably arises from ligand to metal charge transfer band.

¹H NMR spectra :

In order to substantiate the nature of bonding in the metal complexes discussed above, the ¹H NMR (Table 3) and ¹³C NMR (Table 4) spectra of the ligands and their

Table 3. NMR spectral data of the ligands and their metal complexes

Ligands	¹ H NMR spectra (δ ppm)					
	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3 \\ \\ \text{C}=\text{N}- \\ \text{proton} \end{array}$	NH	NH ₂	Aromatic protons	Ring -OH/SO ₂ NH	¹¹ B/ ¹¹⁹ Sn
L ¹ H	1.80	11.20	2.60	7.30–7.70	-	-
L ² H	2.09	11.10	2.70	7.22–7.65	-	-
L ³ H	2.02	9.74	2.80	-	-	-
L ⁴ H	1.98	10.68	2.84	-	-	-
L ⁵ H ₂	1.90	10.42	2.70	6.96–8.22	12.16	-
L ⁶ H ₂	2.02	10.60	3.20	6.80–8.32	12.24	-
L ⁷ H	1.97	10.27	2.98	7.55–6.76	13.00/10.20	-
[PhB(OH)(L ¹)]	2.00	-	2.64	7.34–7.77	-	9.30
[PhB(L ¹) ₂]	2.04	-	2.69	7.44–7.98	-	8.86
[PhB(OH)(L ²)]	2.10	-	2.76	7.26–7.69	-	7.95
[PhB(L ²) ₂]	2.11	-	2.77	7.36–7.89	-	8.56
[PhB(OH)(L ³)]	2.07	-	2.79	-	-	7.59
[PhB(L ³) ₂]	2.05	-	2.83	-	-	8.43
[PhB(OH)(L ⁴)]	2.09	-	2.86	-	-	9.40

Table-3 (contd.)

[PhB(L ⁴) ₂]	2.05	-	2.82	-	-	9.18
[PhB(L ⁵)]	1.98	-	2.75	6.98-8.29	-	8.50
[PhB(L ⁶)]	2.00	-	3.24	6.89-8.38	-	8.52
[PhB(L ⁷) ₂]	2.04	-	2.99	7.06-7.55	-	9.06
[Ph ₂ Si(Cl)(L ¹)]	2.00	-	2.67	7.47-7.98	-	-
[Ph ₂ Si(L ¹) ₂]	2.03	-	2.68	7.66-8.12	-	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(Cl)(L ²)]	2.10	-	2.79	7.46-7.88	-	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ²) ₂]	2.16	-	2.75	7.45-7.99	-	-
[Ph ₂ Si(Cl)(L ³)]	2.00	-	2.80	-	-	-
[Ph ₂ Si(L ³) ₂]	2.02	-	2.81	-	-	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(Cl)(L ⁴)]	1.99	-	2.84	-	-	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ⁴) ₂]	2.00	-	2.85	-	-	-
[Ph ₂ Si(L ⁵)]	2.04	-	2.72	7.08-8.29	-	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ⁶)]	2.10	-	3.22	6.99-8.78	-	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ⁷) ₂]	2.11	-	2.96	7.65-7.96	-	-
[Ph ₂ Sn(Cl)(L ¹)]	2.13	-	2.68	7.66-8.08	-	142.97
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ¹) ₂]	2.07	-	2.65	7.86-8.19	-	250.12
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(Cl)(L ²)]	2.09	-	2.77	7.76-7.96	-	136.66
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ²) ₂]	2.19	-	2.77	7.65-7.90	-	305.75
[Ph ₂ Sn(Cl)(L ³)]	2.20	-	2.86	-	-	149.66
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ³) ₂]	2.07	-	2.83	-	-	342.21
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(Cl)(L ⁴)]	2.09	-	2.81	-	-	160.00
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ⁴) ₂]	2.10	-	2.83	-	-	286.84
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ⁵)]	2.01	-	2.82	7.70-8.88	-	156.45
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ⁶)]	2.05	-	3.27	7.20-8.78	-	159.57
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ⁷) ₂]	2.09	-	2.96	7.95-8.27	-	152.48
[MoO ₂ (L ¹) ₂]	2.18	-	2.67	7.50-8.90	-	-
[MoO ₂ (L ²) ₂]	2.16	-	2.66	7.45-9.00	-	-
[MoO ₂ (L ³) ₂]	2.09	-	2.79	7.97-8.24	-	-
[MoO ₂ (L ⁴) ₂]	2.07	-	2.86	7.80-8.30	-	-
[MoO ₂ (L ⁵)]	2.09	-	2.79	7.99-8.18	-	-
[MoO ₂ (L ⁶)]	2.12	-	3.26	7.87-8.15	-	-
[MoO ₂ (L ⁷) ₂]	1.99	-	2.97	7.89-8.30	-	-

corresponding metal complexes have been recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ using TMS as internal standard. The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands show a signal at δ 9.74–11.20 ppm which is due to NH proton. These NH proton signals disappear in the metal complexes indicating the bond formation through enolic oxygen and thiolic sulfur atom after tautomerization and deprotonation of the ligand molecules. The NH proton of the ring appears at δ 10.67–10.78 ppm in case of ligands which remains unchanged in the metal complexes showing non-involvement of this group in complexation. A sharp singlet due to the OH

Table 4. ¹³C NMR spectral data of the ligands and their metal complexes

Compd.	¹³ C NMR spectra (δ ppm)			
	(>C=N)	(>C=S)	Azomethine methyl carbon	(CH ₃) ₂ M/(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ M/(C ₆ H ₅)B
L ¹ H	160.53	177.50	10.58	-
L ² H	160.53	190.35	10.58	-
L ³ H	185.44	189.64	11.12	-
L ⁴ H	185.44	192.14	11.63	-
L ⁵ H ₂	157.72	168.60	13.78	-
L ⁶ H ₂	162.91	175.84	13.35	-
L ⁷ H	188.76	169.90	10.19	-

Table-4 (contd.)

[PhB(OH)(L ¹)]	161.20	177.50	10.58	-
[PhB(L ¹) ₂]	161.43	177.50	10.58	-
[PhB(OH)(L ²)]	160.90	190.35	10.58	-
[PhB(L ²) ₂]	160.87	190.35	10.58	-
[PhB(OH)(L ³)]	187.04	189.64	11.12	-
[PhB(L ³) ₂]	186.36	189.64	11.12	-
[PhB(OH)(L ⁴)]	186.13	192.14	11.63	-
[PhB(L ⁴) ₂]	186.78	192.14	11.63	-
[PhB(L ⁵)]	157.98	168.60	13.78	-
[PhB(L ⁶)]	164.18	175.84	13.35	-
[PhB(L ⁷) ₂]	189.70	169.90	10.19	-
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(Cl)(L ¹)]	161.27	178.90	11.65	15.84
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ¹) ₂]	161.38	178.64	11.74	15.67
[Ph ₂ Si(Cl)(L ¹)]	161.00	191.67	11.63	17.12
[Ph ₂ Si(L ¹) ₂]	161.27	191.70	10.98	18.05
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(Cl)(L ³)]	187.67	190.54	11.96	15.50
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ³) ₂]	186.79	189.98	12.05	15.43
[Ph ₂ Si(Cl)(L ⁴)]	186.78	193.69	12.84	17.28
[Ph ₂ Si(L ⁴) ₂]	186.40	193.70	12.74	18.00
[Ph ₂ Si(L ⁵)]	158.90	168.99	14.42	17.43
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ⁶)]	164.76	176.80	14.67	15.12
[(CH ₃) ₂ Si(L ⁷) ₂]	189.86	170.45	10.80	15.75
[Ph ₂ Sn(Cl)(L ¹)]	162.14	179.43	11.90	15.26
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ¹) ₂]	162.56	179.56	12.38	15.47
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(Cl)(L ²)]	161.97	193.67	12.90	17.82
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ²) ₂]	161.87	192.70	12.05	17.53
[Ph ₂ Sn(Cl)(L ³)]	187.85	192.49	13.56	15.59
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ³) ₂]	187.77	191.30	13.27	15.43
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(Cl)(L ⁴)]	187.20	194.68	13.98	17.75
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ⁴) ₂]	186.86	195.78	14.47	17.48
[Ph ₂ Sn(L ⁵)]	159.76	168.33	15.18	17.52
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ⁶)]	166.44	178.65	15.85	15.48
[(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L ⁷) ₂]	189.84	171.50	12.25	15.49
[MoO ₂ (L ¹) ₂]	161.35	171.50	12.25	-
[MoO ₂ (L ²) ₂]	161.78	191.74	11.64	-
[MoO ₂ (L ³) ₂]	185.88	189.64	11.12	-
[MoO ₂ (L ⁴) ₂]	185.97	192.14	11.90	-
[MoO ₂ (L ⁵)]	158.32	168.60	14.00	-
[MoO ₂ (L ⁶)]	161.29	175.84	14.84	-
[MoO ₂ (L ⁷) ₂]	189.70	1.69.90	11.59	-

proton of the ring in the ligands at δ 12.24–13.00 ppm disappears in the spectra of metal complexes indicating the complexation through oxygen and nitrogen atom after deprotonation of functional groups of the ligand molecules. The proton signals due to the azomethine methyl protons

(N=C-CH₃) at δ 1.80–2.09 ppm in case of ligands are shifted downfield in the spectra of the metal complexes due to the coordination through the nitrogen atom of the azomethine group. The appearance of a signal due to NH₂ (δ 3.24–3.20 ppm) at almost the same position in the ligands and their corresponding metal complexes show its non-involvement in complex formation. In case of ligands L³H and L⁴H the chemical shift of five protons of unsubstituted cyclopentadienyl ring of ferrocenyl group is observed at δ ~4.15–4.30 ppm as singlet and the proton signals due to the substituted cyclopentadienyl ring appear at δ ~4.45–4.77. Signals due to the substituted cyclopentadienyl ring undergoes downfield shift in the spectra of metal complexes.

¹³C NMR spectra :

The ¹³C NMR spectral data (Table 4) also support the authenticity of the proposed structures. The considerable shifts in the position of carbon atoms adjacent to the azomethine nitrogen (δ 157.72–188.76 ppm), thiolic sulfur (δ 168.60–192.14) and enolic oxygen (δ 168.62–172.50 ppm) support the proposed coordination in the complexes. Thus, the shifts in the positions of carbon atoms adjacent to the coordinating atom clearly indicate the bonding of the azomethine nitrogen, thiolic sulfur and enolic oxygen to the metal atom.

Further, to ascertain the coordination number of boron and tin, the ¹¹B NMR and ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra of some complexes have been recorded in Table 3. The strong intensity signals observed in the region, δ 7.59–9.30 ppm in the ¹¹B NMR spectra of boron complexes and at δ 136.66 to 160.00 ppm and δ 250.12 to 342.21 ppm and in the ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra of the organotin(IV) complexes clearly showing the expected coordination environments, around the metal atom. Similarly the ²⁹Si NMR spectra of the complexes giving the signals at δ 95–90 ppm and 110–130 ppm and which are indicative of penta- and hexa-coordinated states of the silicon atom in the corresponding tri- and di-organosilicon complexes, respectively.

ESR spectra :

The ESR spectra of manganese(II) complexes were recorded at room temperature. These consist of a single broad peak and from which the Lande splitting factor ('g' values) has been calculated which lie in the range 2.0043–

2.2034 (Table 5). These values are characteristic of tetrahedral geometry. The effective magnetic moment recorded at room temperature for the manganese(II) complex is close to the predicted values for five unpaired electrons in the metal ion. The observed magnetic moment value of 5.96–6.23 B.M. indicates that manganese(II) complexes are paramagnetic in nature consisting five unpaired electrons.

Table 5. ESR spectral data of the manganese(II) complexes

Compd.	ESR spectral data			
	H_0	g^{II} value	Temp. (°C)	m.W. Frequency (v)
[MnCl(L ¹)(H ₂ O)]	3350.25	2.0548	25	9.38
[Mn(L ²) ₂]	3255.65	2.0055	25	9.38
[MnCl(L ³)(H ₂ O)]	3350.72	2.0400	25	9.38
[Mn(L ⁴) ₂]	3364.57	2.0075	25	9.38
[Mn(L ⁵)H ₂ O]	3285.02	2.0043	25	9.38
[Mn(L ⁶)H ₂ O]	3294.66	2.0340	25	9.38
[Mn(L ⁷) ₂]	3217.21	2.2034	25	9.38

X-Ray structure determination :

The possible geometry of the finely powdered products has been deduced on the basis of X-ray powder diffraction studies. The observed interplanar spacing values ('d' in Å) for [(Mn(O[^]N[^]X)H₂O)] complex have been measured and the Miller indices *h*, *k* and *l* have been assigned to each *d* value and 2-Theta angles are reported in Table 6. The results show that the compound belongs to 'Orthorhombic' crystal system³⁵ having unit cell pa-

Table 6. X-Ray diffraction data of the [(Mn(O[^]N[^]X)H₂O)] complex

Peak no.	2θ (deg.) (obs.)	<i>h</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>d</i> -spacing (obs.) (Å)
1	15.37	2	2	0	7.249
2	16.93	3	0	1	6.591
3	22.60	5	1	0	4.942
4	25.82	4	3	0	4.331
5	27.45	5	2	1	4.081
6	30.75	3	4	1	3.652
7	31.93	3	3	2	3.521
8	37.92	7	3	1	2.981
9	42.22	4	3	3	2.692
10	44.63	10	1	0	2.550
11	46.34	2	7	0	2.462
12	48.21	8	5	0	2.373

rameters as *a* = 24.563, *b* = 18.465 and *c* = 10.768 and Alpha = 90°, Beta = 90°, Gamma = 90°. The X-ray powder diffraction studies for [(MoO₂(O[^]N[^]X))] complex show that the compound belongs to 'Orthorhombic' crystal system³⁵ having unit cell parameters as *a* = 32.50, *b* = 13.00, *c* = 19.80 and Alpha = 90°, Beta = 90°, Gamma = 90°. The Miller indices (*h*, *k*, *l*), *d*-spacing value and 2-Theta angles are reported in Table 7. The X-ray powder diffraction studies for [PhB(O[^]N[^]X))] complex show that the compound belongs to 'Orthorhombic' crystal system³⁵ having unit cell parameters as *a* = 9.85, *b* = 18.50, *c* = 27.26 maximum deviation of 2-Theta = 0.018 and Alpha = 90°, Beta = 90°, Gamma = 90°. The Miller indices (*h*, *k*, *l*), *d*-spacing value and 2-Theta angles are reported in Table 8. The X-ray powder diffraction study of the compound [(C₆H₅)₂Sn(O[^]N[^]X)] has been carried out to determine its molecular symmetry. The observed interplaner spacing values, *d* (Å), the Miller indices *h*, *k* and *l* and 2-Theta angles are given in

Table 7. X-Ray diffraction data of the [(MoO₂(O[^]N[^]X))] complex

Peak no.	2θ (deg.) (obs.)	<i>h</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>d</i> -spacing (obs.) (Å)
1	12.7	4	1	0	6.9640
2	17.9	0	0	4	4.9510
3	19.0	0	2	3	4.6430
4	21.4	8	0	0	4.1110
5	22.5	0	3	2	3.9660
6	26.5	7	0	4	3.4110
7	26.7	9	1	2	3.3120
8	32.4	10	0	2	3.1190
9	28.3	8	2	6	2.7780
10	41.5	4	4	4	2.5830
11	46.3	4	6	0	2.1250

Table 8. X-Ray diffraction data of the [PhB(O[^]N[^]X))] complex

Peak no.	2θ (deg.) (obs.)	<i>h</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>d</i> -spacing (obs.) (Å)
1	9.7	0	1	0	9.203
2	10.7	2	1	1	8.2610
3	12.1	1	1	2	7.3081
4	16.4	1	2	3	5.4004
5	17.5	0	3	3	5.0633
6	18.0	2	0	0	4.9236
7	19.5	0	4	0	4.5483

Table 9. The data suggest an orthorhombic primitive type lattice to this tin derivative. The having unit cell parameters as $a = 16.58272$, $b = 11.15426$, $c = 6.78430$. A maximum deviation of $2\text{-Theta} = 0.018$ and $\text{Alpha} = 90^\circ$, $\text{Beta} = 90^\circ$, $\text{Gamma} = 90^\circ$.

Table 9. X-Ray diffraction data of the $[(C_6H_5)_2Sn(O^N^O^X)]$ complex

Peak no.	2θ (deg.) (obs.)	h	k	l	d -spacing (obs.) (Å)
1	16.580	0	1	0	6.86904
2	19.648	1	0	1	5.37215
3	24.326	3	1	0	4.02014
4	26.145	0	0	1	3.97613
5	30.028	2	2	5	3.72142
6	35.954	5	0	0	3.53816
7	39.682	0	3	1	3.32714
8	44.316	6	1	0	2.83502
9	48.916	3	2	2	2.68392
10	53.701	6	3	0	2.54129
11	58.590	1	1	3	2.33682
12	63.285	9	0	0	2.14952
13	69.768	1	6	1	1.73162
14	75.464	2	4	3	1.62084
15	80.920	0	6	2	1.48758
16	84.764	7	6	0	1.46217
17	86.215	1	7	2	1.38142
18	89.516	2	2	0	1.37426

Thus on the basis of the above spectral factors, as well as the analytical data, tetra coordinated geometry has been established for the organoboron complexes (Figs. 8 and 9). The tetrahedral and pseudo-octahedral/octahedral geometry has been suggested for the manganese (Figs. 10, 11) and dioxomolybdenum complexes (Figs. 12, 13), respectively, trigonal bipyramidal and octahedral geometries have been established for the organosilicon(IV) and organotin(IV) complexes (Figs. 14 and 15), respectively.

Antimicrobial assay :

The ligands and their metal complexes were evaluated for their antimicrobial activity against the bacteria, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, and the fungi, *Alternaria alternata*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum*. The results were compared with those of the standard drug Streptomycin for bacteria and Flucanazole for fungi. The results are summarized in Graphs

Fig. 8. Boron complexes of ligands (L^1H-L^4H).

Fig. 9. Boron complexes of ligands ($L^5H_2-L^6H_2$).

Fig. 10. Manganese complexes of ligands (L^1H-L^4H).

Manganese complex
(1 : 1)
where, X = O, N or S

Fig. 11. Manganese complexes of ligands ($L^5H_2-L^6H_2$).

Molybdenum complex
(1:2)

Fig. 12. Molybdenum complexes of ligands (L^1H-L^4H).

Molybdenum complex
(1 : 1)
where, X = O, N or S

Fig. 13. Molybdenum complexes of ligands ($L^5H_2-L^6H_2$).

1-6. The inferences drawn from these graphs clearly indicate that sulfur containing ligands (L^2H , L^4H and L^6H_2)

Silicon and Tin Complexes
(1:1)

Silicon and Tin Complexes
(1:2)

Fig. 14. Silicon and tin complexes of ligands (L^1H-L^4H).

Silicon and tin complexes
(1 : 1)
where, X = O, N or S
R' = CH₃ or C₆H₅
M = Si and Sn

Fig. 15. Silicon and tin complexes of ligands (L^7H).

Fig. 16. *Helicoverpa armigera* (Adult and larva) on healthy cotton plant.

are more active against various pathogenic fungi and bacteria than oxygen containing ligands (L^1H , L^3H and L^5H_2). The increased activity of these ligands may be explained

Fig. 17. Cottonboll damage by *Helicoverpa armigera* larva.

Graph 1. Antibacterial activity of metal complexes with ligands (L^1H and L^2H).

Graph 2. Antibacterial activity of metal complexes with ligands (L^3H and L^4H).

Graph 3. Antibacterial activity of metal complexes with ligands (L^5H_2 and L^6H_2).

Graph 4. Antifungal activity of metal complexes with ligands (L^1H and L^2H).

Graph 5. Antifungal activity of metal complexes with ligands (L^3H and L^4H).

Graph 6. Antifungal activity of metal complexes with ligands (L^5H_2 and L^6H_2).

on the basis that sulfur (as donor atom) containing compounds are more toxic than the oxygen containing compounds. It has been suggested that ligands with N and S donor system might have inhibited the enzyme production. In general biological activity of such type of compounds enhances considerably on complexation with metal atom⁶². The results also show that the metal complexes have more inhibitory effect than do the parent ligands,

Graph 7. Pesticidal activity of metal complexes with ligands (L^5H_2 and L^6H_2) against *Helicoverpa armigera*.

Graph 8. Pesticidal activity of metal complexes with ligands (L^5H_2 and L^6H_2) against *Spodoptera litura*.

Graph 9. Pesticidal activity of metal complexes with ligands (L^7H) against *Chorotogonus trachypterus*.

due to the chelation^{63,64} of metal atom with the ligand moieties. Chelation tends to make a ligand a more potent antimicrobial agent. This increased activity upon chelation is attributed to the positive charge of the metal partially shared with donor atoms present on the ligands⁶⁵ and there is electron delocalization over the whole chelate ring. This, in turn, increases the lipophilic character

Graph 10. Pesticidal activity (Brinjal-leaf spot disease caused by *Alternaria alternata*) of metal complexes with ligands (L^5H_2).

Graph 11. Pesticidal activity (Brinjal-leaf spot disease caused by *Alternaria alternata*) of metal complexes with ligands (L^6H_2).

Graph 12. Pesticidal activity (Bajra-rust disease caused by *Puccinia penniciti*) of metal complexes with ligands (L^3H).

Graph 13. Pesticidal activity (Bajra-rust disease caused by *Puccinia penniciti*) of metal complexes with ligands (L^4H).

Graph 14. Pesticidal activity (Bajra-disease ergot on earhead caused by *Cleveiceps fusiformis*) of metal complexes with ligands (L^5H_2).

Graph 15. Pesticidal activity (Bajra-disease ergot on earhead caused by *Cleveiceps fusiformis*) of metal complexes with ligands (L^6H_2).

Graph 16. Pesticidal activity (Guar-disease guar blight by *Alternaria symopsidae*) of metal complexes with ligands (L^4H_1).

of the metal chelate and favours its permeation through the lipid layers of the bacterial membranes⁶⁶. Generally, it is suggested that the chelated complexes deactivate various cellular enzymes, which play a vital role in various metabolic pathways of these microorganisms. Other factors such as solubility, conductivity and dipole moment,

Fig. 18. The newly hatched caterpillars of *Spodoptera litura* still under the protection of irregular fluffy mass and Cotton-leaf damage by *Spodoptera litura* larva.

Fig. 19. Adult *Chorotogonous trachypterus* on healthy cotton plant.

Fig. 20. Pesticidal activity (Mustard-leaf spot disease caused by *Alternaria alternata*) of metal complexes with ligands (L^5H_2 and L^6H_2).

affected by the presence of metal ions, may also increase the biological activity of the metal complexes compared to the ligand.

Fig. 21. Pesticidal activity (Bajra-rust disease caused by *Puccinia penniciti*) of ligands (L^3H and L^4H).

Fig. 22. Pesticidal activity (Bajra-rust disease caused by *Puccinia penniciti*) of organosilicon(IV) complexes with ligands (L^3H and L^4H).

Fig. 23. Pesticidal activity (Bajra-rust disease caused by *Puccinia penniciti*) of organotin(IV) complexes with ligands (L^3H and L^4H).

Pesticidal activity and nematicidal activity :

The pesticidal activity of synthesized compounds was evaluated *in vitro* conditions (Graphs 7, 8 and 9) against three adult beetles *Chorotogonus trachypterus*, *Helicoverpa armigera* and *Spodoptera litura* and *in vivo* conditions (Graphs 10, 11, 12, 13, 14 15 and 16) against dif-

Fig. 24. Disease ergot of Bajra earhead showing sclerotia caused by *Cleviceps fusiformis*.

Fig. 25. Pesticidal activity (Bajra-disease ergot on earhead caused by *Cleviceps fusiformis*) of ligand (L^6H_2).

Fig. 26. Pesticidal activity (Bajra-disease ergot on earhead caused by *Cleviceps fusiformis*) of organosilicon(IV) complexes with ligand (L^6H_2).

Fig. 27. Pesticidal activity (Bajra-disease ergot on earhead caused by *Cleviceps fusiformis*) of organotin(IV) complexes with ligand (L^6H_2).

Graph 17. Nematicidal activity (Ovicidal action) of metal complexes with ligands (L^5H_2 and L^6H_2).

Graph 18. Nematicidal activity (Larvicidal action) of metal complexes with ligands (L^5H_2 and L^6H_2).

ferent crop plants for the ligands (L^3H , L^4H , L^5H_2 , L^6H_2 and L^7H) and their metal complexes. The results of pesticidal activity reveal that the ligands and their metal complexes showed good pesticidal activity. All the compounds are fairly active in killing the pests (Figs. 16, 17, 18 and 19) and controlling the disease in crop plants (Figs. 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26 and 27). It was observed that there

Graph 19. Nematicidal activity (Pupicidal action) of metal complexes with ligands (L^5H_2 and L^6H_2).

Graph 20. Nematicidal activity (Adulticidal action) of metal complexes with ligands (L^5H_2 and L^6H_2).

was an appreciable increase in the pesticidal activities in case of metal complexes compared to the uncomplexed ligands. Tin complexes were found to be the most effective as evidenced from the comparative study of their percentage mortality data with other metal chelates⁶⁷.

The objective of nematode control is to improve growth and yield of plants, which can be achieved through reduction of the nematode population in soil or in plants, or through reduction of their damage. From the results of nematicidal activity, maximum hatching was recorded in the control but in the eggs treated with the ligands as well as metal complexes, low hatching was recorded. The results in Graphs 17, 18, 19 and 20 reveal that the activity increases on complexation and chelation, i.e. the newly synthesized complexes have been found to be more active in lowering the hatching of eggs and increasing the ovicidal, larvicidal, pupicidal and adulticidal mortality than

Table 10. Effect of the ligand L⁴H and its metal complexes on germination of gram (*Cicer arretinum*) as length

Compd.	Wet length of seedling (cm)						Dry length of seedling (cm)					
	Root (conc. in ppm)			Shoot (conc. in ppm)			Root (conc. in ppm)			Shoot (conc. in ppm)		
	5	10	25	5	10	25	5	10	25	5	10	25
L ⁴ H	9.8	10.3	5.8	7.1	7.7	5.4	9.7	10.0	5.9	7.1	7.7	5.4
[PhB(OH)(L ⁴)]	10.9	11.7	6.7	7.8	8.4	6.4	10.6	10.8	6.8	7.8	8.5	6.5
[PhB(L ⁴) ₂]	10.7	11.5	6.5	7.6	8.1	6.0	10.4	10.6	6.6	7.6	8.1	6.0
[MnCl(L ⁴)H ₂ O]	11.1	11.9	7.5	8.2	8.7	6.7	10.8	11.6	7.1	8.2	8.7	6.7
[Mn(L ⁴) ₂]	10.9	11.7	7.3	8.0	8.4	6.5	10.5	11.3	7.0	8.0	8.3	6.5
[MoO ₂ (L ⁴) ₂]	10.4	11.2	6.3	7.4	8.2	6.0	10.3	10.4	6.3	7.5	8.2	6.0
Control	8.8			6.2			8.2			5.8		

Table 11. Effect of the ligand L⁴H and its metal complexes on germination of gram (*Cicer arretinum*) as weight

Compd.	Wet weight of seedling (g)						Dry weight of seedling (g)					
	Root (conc. in ppm)			Shoot (conc. in ppm)			Root (conc. in ppm)			Shoot (conc. in ppm)		
	5	10	25	5	10	25	5	10	25	5	10	25
L ⁴ H	2.38	2.73	2.01	3.97	4.26	2.76	1.32	1.58	0.88	2.43	2.14	1.75
[PhB(OH)(L ⁴)]	2.76	3.33	2.62	4.72	5.12	3.70	1.86	1.88	1.12	2.92	3.02	2.24
[PhB(L ⁴) ₂]	2.73	3.27	2.35	4.63	4.97	3.62	1.72	1.79	1.08	2.88	2.98	1.91
[MnCl(L ⁴)H ₂ O]	2.81	3.50	2.74	4.84	5.33	3.81	1.88	2.15	1.19	2.98	3.17	2.46
[Mn(L ⁴) ₂]	2.75	3.41	2.60	4.74	5.27	3.74	1.80	2.06	1.11	2.88	3.10	2.41
[MoO ₂ (L ⁴) ₂]	2.56	2.98	2.43	4.23	4.76	2.99	1.66	1.86	1.46	2.95	2.58	2.16
Control	2.24			3.85			0.90			1.43		

Fig. 28. Effect of the ligand L⁴H and manganese(II) metal complexes on germination of gram (*Cicer arretinum*) as weight.

Fig. 29. Effect of the ligand L⁴H and molybdenum metal complexes on germination of gram (*Cicer arretinum*) as weight.

Fig. 30. Effect of the ligand L⁴H and manganese(II) metal complexes on germination of gram (*Cicer arretinum*) as length.

The pesticidal activity and nematocidal activity shown by the metal complexes is in the following order :

Boron complexes < Organosilicon(IV) complexes < Organotin(IV) complexes.

Plant growth regulating activity :

The results of the plant growth regulating activity are

the parent ligand itself. It is interesting to note that as the concentration increases, the activity increases.

Fig. 31. Effect of the ligand L^4H and molybdenum(II) metal complexes on germination of gram (*Cicer arietinum*) as length.

recorded in Tables 10 and 11. The data summarized in the tables revealed that the ligand and its metal complexes show plant growth regulating activity only at optimum concentrations (5 ppm). The activity has been recorded in terms of a decrease in the growing period and an increase in the wet and dry weight (Figs. 28 and 29) and length (Figs. 30 and 31) of the seedling. The activity of the ligand increases on complexation with the metals due to the presence of micronutrients, which are essential for the plant growth.

Conclusions

- From the analytical data and spectral studies, the ligands (L^1H-L^4H and L^7H) coordinate in a monobasic bidentate manner and ligands ($L^5H_2-L^6H_2$) coordinate in a dibasic tridentate manner with metal ion.
- Boron complexes synthesized in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar reactions with ligands (L^1H-L^4H and L^7H) and in 1 : 1 molar reactions with ligands ($L^5H_2-L^6H_2$) were found to be with tetra coordinated geometry.
- Manganese complexes synthesized in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar reactions with ligands (L^1H-L^4H and L^7H) and in 1 : 1 molar reactions with ligands ($L^5H_2-L^6H_2$) were found to be with tetra coordinated geometry.
- Molybdenum complexes synthesized in 1 : 2 molar reactions with ligands (L^1H-L^4H and L^7H) and

in 1 : 1 molar reactions with ligands ($L^5H_2-L^6H_2$) were found to be having octahedral geometry.

- Silicon and tin complexes synthesized in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar reactions with ligands (L^1H-L^4H and L^7H) and in 1 : 1 molar reactions with ligands ($L^5H_2-L^6H_2$) were found to be trigonal bipyramid and hexa coordinated geometry.
- Antimicrobial activity of the complexes and the ligands showed that the complexes are more active than the parent ligands and the data reveal that the sulfur containing complexes were found to be more active than the other complexes.
- The results reveal that the unimolar metal complexes have less nematocidal activity and pesticidal activity than the bimolar metal complexes, perhaps due to the presence of two ligand moieties in these complexes.
- Dimethyl metal complexes are also less active, as compared to the diphenyl metal complexes. The reason for this seems, because phenyl groups are highly effective against root-knot nematode and crop and plant damaging pests than methyl groups.

Acknowledgement

I am extremely grateful to CSIR, New Delhi for financial assistance in the form of Grant no. 01(2571)/12/EMR-II for doing the mentioned research and for the Council of Indian Chemical Society, Kolkata for awarding me this very prestigious award.

References

1. K. L. Morrison and G. A. Weiss, *Nat. Chem. Biol.*, 2007, **2**, 3.
2. R. V. Singh, L. Dawara and M. Swami, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **89**, 1093.
3. P. Kapoor, R. V. Singh and N. Fahmi, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2012, **65**, 262.
4. R. K. Ramakrishana, R. K. Madhusudan and K. N. Mahendra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2006, **45**, 377.
5. P. Kapoor, N. Fahmi and R. V. Singh, *Spectrochim. Acta A, Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.*, 2011, **83**, 74.
6. R. Garg, M. K. Saini, N. Fahmi and R. V. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 2433.
7. G. Venkatachalam, S. Maheswaran and R. Ramesh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2005, **44**, 705.
8. Y. J. Hamada, *Trans. Electron Devices*, 1997, **44**, 1208.

9. S. A. Anna Zidan, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon*, 2003, **178**, 567.
10. N. Sari, S. Arslan, E. Logoglu and I. Sakiyan, *G. U. J. Sci.*, 2003, 283.
11. M. K. Biyala, K. Sharma, M. Swami, N. Fahmi and R. V. Singh, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2008, **33**, 377.
12. M. K. Biyala, K. Sharma, N. Fahmi and R. V. Singh, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon and the Related Elements*, 2007, **182**, 2955.
13. R. Rajavel, M. S. Vadivu and C. Anitha, *E-J. Chem.*, 2008, **5**, 620.
14. Z. H. Chohan, M. Arif and M. Sarfraz, *Appl. Organomet. Chem.*, 2007, **21**, 294.
15. K. Sharma, S. C. Joshi and R. V. Singh, *Met. Based Drugs*, 2000, **7**, 105.
16. S. K. Sridhar, S. N. Pandeya and E. De Clercq, *Bollettino Chimico Farmaceutico*, 2001, **140**, 302.
17. S. K. Sridhar and A. Ramesh, *Indian Drugs*, 2001, **38**, 174.
18. H. Tarafder, A. Kasbollah, N. Saravanan, K. A. Crouse, A. M. Ali and K. T. Oo, *J. Biochem. Mol. Biol. Biophys.*, 2002, **6**, 85.
19. S. Ren, R. Wang, K. Komatsu, P. Bonaz-Krause, Y. Zyrianov, C. E. Mckenna, C. Csipke, Z. A. Tokes and E. J. Lien, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **45**, 410.
20. S. B. Desai, P. B. Desai and K. R. Desai, *Heterocycl. Commun.*, 2001, **7**, 83.
21. M. Motevalli, P. O. Brien, J. R. Walsh and I. M. Watson, *Polyhedron*, 1996, **15**, 2801.
22. M. R. Maurya, N. Bharti, F. Naqui, A. Bhattacharya, S. Bhattacharya and A. Azam, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2000, **35**, 481.
23. P. N. Saxena and S. Saxena, *Appl. Organomet. Chem.*, 1989, **3**, 279.
24. M. K. Yang and Y. G. Kim, *J. Toxicol. Environ. Health A*, 1999, **58**, 289.
25. V. Gevorgyan, L. Borisova, A. Vyater, V. Ryabova and E. Luckevics, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1997, **548**, 149.
26. R. Tacle and B. Becker, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1992, **438**, 45.
27. T. Tschamber, S. Adam, Y. Matsuya, S. Masuda, N. Ohsawa, S. Maruyama, K. Kamoshita, H. Nemoto and J. Eustache, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2007, **17**, 5101.
28. L. S. Pavarov and O. D. Ryazahova, *Zh. Obshch. Khim.*, 1972, **42**, 1010.
29. L. Deng, H. Wu, B. Yu, M. Jiang and W. Wu, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2004, **14**, 2781.
30. S. J. Baker, Y. K. Zhang and T. Akama, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2006, **49**, 4447.
31. T. Akama, S. J. Baker and Y. K. Zhang, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2009, **19**, 2129.
32. E. Seiradake, W. Mao and V. Hernandez, *J. Mol. Biol.*, 2009, **390**, 196.
33. Y. Xia, K. Cao and Y. Zhou, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2011, **21**, 2533.
34. H. M. Guo, G. L. Zhao and Y. Y. Yu, *Chinese J. Inorg. Chem.*, **24**, 1393.
35. Y. Y. Yu, G. L. Zhao and Y. H. Wen, *Chinese J. Struct. Chem.*, 2007, **26**, 1395.
36. G. C. Dismukes and R. T'van Willigen, "Manganese : The Oxygen-Evolving Complex and Models, Encyclopedia of Inorganic Chemistry", 2006.
37. J. C. Hilton and K. V. Rajagopalan, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1996, **325**, 143.
38. H. Schindelin, C. Kisker, J. Hilton, K. V. Rajagopalan and D. C. Rees, *Science*, 1996, **272**, 1615.
39. K. M. Chan, S. Mukund, A. Kletzin, M. W. W. Adams and D. C. Rees, *Science*, 1995, **267**, 1463.
40. G. N. George, J. Hilton and K. V. Rajagopalan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **118**, 1113.
41. R. V. Singh and M. K. Biyala, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon*, 2006, **181**, 1477.
42. Rekha Garg, M. K. Saini, N. Fahmi and R. V. Singh, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2006, **31**, 362.
43. A. I. Vogel, "A Textbook of Organic Quantitative Analysis", 5th ed., Pearson Education Ltd., UK, 2004, 243.
44. A. I. Vogel, "A Textbook of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 6th ed., Pearson Education Ltd., UK, 2006, 498.
45. A. I. Vogel, "A Textbook of Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 6th ed., Pearson Education Ltd., UK, 2006, 387.
46. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., Longmans Green ELBS, London, 1968.
47. R. Garg, N. Fahmi and R. V. Singh, *Russian J. Coord. Chem.*, 2008, **34**, 198.
48. R. V. Singh, P. Chaudhary, S. Chauhan and M. Swami, *Spectrochim. Acta Part A : Mol. and Biomol. Spectrosc.*, 2009, **72**, 260.
49. S. Gaur, N. Fahmi and R. V. Singh, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon*, 2007, **182**, 853.
50. J. B. Chauhan, R. B. Subramanian and P. K. Sanyal, *Ind. J. Environ. Toxicol.*, 2002, **12**, 22.
51. M. Jain, D. Kumar and R. V. Singh, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 2003, **26**, 99.
52. M. Jain and R. V. Singh, *Appl. Organometal. Chem.*, 2003, **17**, 616.

53. P. M. Davidson and M. E. Parish, *Food Technology*, 1989, **43**, 148.
54. M. M. Ali, M. Jesmin, S. M. A. Salam, J. A. Khanam, M. F. Islam and M. N. Islam, *J. Sci. Res.*, 2009, **1**, 641.
55. L. Dawara, D. Singh and R. V. Singh, *Main Group Met. Chem.*, 2011, **34**, 69.
56. M. Jain, S. Maanju and R. V. Singh, *Appl. Organometal. Chem.*, 2004, **18**, 471.
57. V. P. Singh, R. V. Singh and J. P. Tandon, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1989, **19**, 669.
58. M. Sonmeza, M. Celebib, A. Leventb, I. Berberc and Z. Senturkb, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2010, **63**, 1986.
59. L. Lang and J. Dianzeng, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Nano Met. Chem.*, 2005, **35**, 264.
60. K. Kulkarni, P. G. Avaji, G. B. Bagihalli, S. A. Patil and P. S. Badami, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 481.
61. S. Chandra and R. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B.* 1988, **27**, 417.
62. J. R. J. Sorenson, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1976, **19**, 135.
63. B. G. Tweedy, *Phytopathol.*, 1964, **55**, 910.
64. A. L. Lehninger, *Biochem.*, 2nd ed., 1975, 519.
65. B. Keshavan and H. Kempe Gowda, *Turk. J. Chem.*, 2002, **26**, 237.
66. A. W. Varnes, R. B. Dodson and E. L. Wehry, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 946.
67. R. S. Champawat and R. S. Sharma, *J. Mycol. and Pl. Path.*, 2003, **33**, 290.

